
COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF THE BACTEROCIN PRODUCING CHARACTERISTICS OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA FROM SELECTED TRADITIONAL FERMENTED FOODS

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ABSTRACT

Lactic acid bacteria from freshly prepare ‘Ogi’ and ‘Kunun’ were isolated by plating on nutrient agar modified with glacial acetic acid. The identification of the isolates was carried out using biochemical methods. The identified isolates (*Lactobacillus planetarium*, *Lactobacillus sake*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus fermentum*) were screened for their ability to produce bacterocin against food borne pathogens (*Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) using the pour plate method. The isolated organisms inhibited different food borne pathogens with different zones of inhibition. The highest was exhibited by *Lactobacillus fermentum* on *Escherichia coli* (38mm) while the least was by *Lactobacillus acidophilus* on *Staphylococcus aureus* (18mm). Fresh Ogi constituted a better source of lactic acid bacteria than that of Kunun. The antimicrobial activity of the four LAB strains was inactivated by the addition of proteinase K, thus confirming the proteinaceous nature of the inhibition. The bacterocin of lactic acid bacteria have potential application for assessing and improving food quality, and safety

KEYWORDS: Bacterocin, Food, Lactic Acid bacteria, Ogi, Kunun.

INTRODUCTION

Lactic acid bacteria are important groups of microorganisms involved in good fermentations (Cintas 2001). They have beneficial influence on the nutritional organoleptic and shelf stability of goods they are generally regarded as safe and can be used as natural competitive inhibit loss of microbiota or as starter cultures under controlled conditions (Cintas et al., 2001). They are able to produce small organic substances that contribute to aroma and give specific organoleptic attributes to foods (Caplice and Fitzgerald, 1999). Protection of goods from spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms by LAB is through the production of organic acids, hydrogen peroxide, diacetyl, bacterocin and other compounds as metabolites (Messens and De Vugst, 2000; Deraz et al., 2005; Carr et al., 2002, Savadogo et al., 2004). Lactic acid bacteria are non motile, non sporulating. They lack cytochrome and obtain energy by substrate level phosphorylation. They ferment sugars. Nutritionally, fastidious and need many vitamins, amino acids, purines and pyrimidines (Prescott et al., 2006). Lactobacilli produce lactic acid as a major or sole fermentation product. Streptococcus, Enterococci, Lactococcus, Lactobacilli and Leuconostoc are members of this group of bacteria.

Justification of the work: The health benefit of probiotic foods cannot be over emphasized. Currently probiotic organisms containing foods are being developed into commercial food supplements in most developed countries. Nigeria indigenous fermented foods with probiotic potentials properties remain under exploited. This is the trust of this work.

Aim: To determine and compare the level of the bacterocin in the selected indigenous fermented foods and to established probiotic potentials of these fermented local foods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

The samples for this research work were purchased from Umuahia Central Market. Bacterocin and proteinase K. were obtained from IITA Ibadan, Nigeria. All chemicals and reagents were of the analytical grade reagents. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E.coli* were obtained from Federal Medical Center Umuahia Abia State Nigerian as clinical isolates

Preparation of samples for isolation of Lactic acid bacteria:

Ogi, and Kunun used for this research work were prepared using traditional methods. Ogi from maize was prepared after cleaning, steeping, wet milling and sieving of the pomace using muslin cloth. Kunun was processed from millet by steeping for 48h, wet milling, sieving through muslin cloth, followed by gelatinization of part of the sediment after which it was mixed with the un-gelatinized portion. The resultant sample was fermented for 24h.

Media preparation:

Nutrient agar which was used as the isolation medium was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions. However, it was acidified with 1% glacial acetic acid (to allow the growth of lactic acid bacteria and to inhibit the growth of other microorganisms).

Isolation of lactic acid bacteria:

One gram each of the fermenting Ogi and Kunun samples were collected with the wire loop and streaked on the surface of the sterile media. The plates were incubated aerobically for 24h at 37°C. After incubation, Catalase test was conducted on each of the observed colonies (Onyeagba, 2004). Catalase negative colonies were sub cultured until a pure culture was obtained.

Identification and Characterization of Isolates:

Obtained isolates were identified and characterized using standard microbiological and biochemical procedures (Buchanan and Gibbons, 1974). Each bacterial colony was observed for morphological features such as Colour, edge of the colony, consistency, elevation and presence of pigments.

Gram Staining:

A smear was made by emulsifying the test organism on a drop of normal saline and was allowed to dry. It was fixed horizontally over a Bunsen flame. On cooling, it was flooded with crystal violet solution, allowed to stand for one minute and rinsed with distilled water. Acetone/alcohol solution was used to decolorize the cells and they were rinsed immediately with distilled water. Subsequently, it was covered with Lugol's iodine (mordant) for one minute and rinsed with distilled water. The smear was counterstained with safranin for 30 seconds, rinsed with distilled water and allowed to dry. The stained smear was observed under the microscope using oil immersion objective (x 100). Only the gram positive isolates were used for further work.

Biochemical Tests:

Catalase test:

A loopful of the culture was placed on a clean grease free slide and drops of 3% hydrogen peroxide were placed on the culture. Immediate formation of gas bubbles indicated a positive reaction while absence of gas bubbles indicated a negative reaction. (Buchanan and Gibbons 1974). Only the catalase negative cultures were used for further work.

Motility test:

A quantity of 1.8g of the nutrient agar medium was added to 50ml distilled water and heated to achieve complete dissolution. The solution was dispersed into clean test tubes in 10ml aliquots and sterilized at 121°C for 15 min. They were cooled in slants and the inoculated with pure isolates. The samples were subsequently incubated at 37°C for 48h. Diffuse growth away from the line of inoculation showed motility while growth along the inoculation line showed non motility.

Oxidase test:

A few drops of a redox dye tetra-methyl-p-phenyldiamine were placed on a filter paper in a Petri dish and a smear of inoculums of the test culture was made on the filter paper. Purple coloration within 5-10 seconds indicated a positive Oxidase test (Buchanan and Gibbons, 1974).

Coagulase test:

Side Coagulase was made by picking few colonies from the culture of test isolates and emulsifying them on lighter drops of normal saline on a clean grease free slide to form a smooth milky suspension. A loopful of blood plasma was added to the suspensions. Clump formation within 10 seconds indicated a positive result (Buchanan and Gibbons, 1974).

Arginine test:

Arginine broth was inoculated with freshly prepared isolates and incubated for 24h before Nessler's reagent was added to it. Arginine hydrolysis was indicated by the development of a brown Colour (Onyeagba, 2004).

Nitrate reduction test:

Nitrate broth (5ml) was inoculated with fresh isolates and incubated for 5 days. Gas formation in Durham tubes was noted. Appearance of a red Colour after the addition of reagent indicated the reduction of nitrates.

Growth development:

Isolates of candidate microorganisms were streaked on sterile nutrient agar plates and the plates were incubated at 37°C for 3 days.

Sugar fermentation tests:

This test was carried out to determine the ability of microorganisms to metabolize sugar with the production of acid or gas. The test sugars were glucose, Arabinose, Galactose, lactose, maltose, mannitol and sucrose. Peptone water was used as the fermentation medium. One (1g of each sugar was dissolved in 25ml of peptone water and 10ml portions were dispensed into sterilized test tubes. Each tube contained an inverted Durham tube. The test tubes were sterilized by autoclaving and inoculated with pure culture before incubation at 37°C for 72h, a change in Colour from dark green to light pink indicated acid production while gas production was indicated by the downward displacement of the liquids in the Durham tubes.

Screening for bacterocin producing activity:

The test organisms were inoculated into 5ml of MRS broth and were incubated at 30°C for 18h. The pH of the culture was adjusted to 6.2 with sterile 1ml NaOH and centrifuged at 3000rpm for 15min and then decanted into sterile test tube to get cell free supernatant. The target organisms; *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella* were grown in MacConkey and Nutrient broth respectively for 16h and serially diluted. Using a sterile 1ml syringe, 0.1ml per 100ml agar was taken from the 10⁻⁷ dilutant and added to semi-solid tryptone soy, MacConkey and nutrient agar. Subsequently, 40ml of each of those media were poured into sterile Petri dishes and left to solidify. Agar cells were aseptically bored inside the agar and 1ml of the cell-free supernatant were poured into each well and incubated for 24h after which they were observed for zones of inhibition and the diameter noted (AOAC, 1990). Inhibition was indicated as positive when the inhibition halo of the indicator strains above the LAB colonies were more than 2mm and such bacteria were considered as potential bacterocin producers.

Determination of mode of inhibitory action of bacterocin:

Proteinase K from human album from (Sigma Aldrich Chemie Germany) was prepared to give a clear colorless solution (30ug/ml). One (1) ml of proteinase K was inoculated into 1ml of overnight broth culture of *Staph aureus* and *E. coli* and was spread evenly on agar plates. The plates were incubated for 24h at 37°C and checked for inhibition zones.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 1 shows the morphological characteristics of lactic acid bacteria isolated from the fermented food products Ogi and Kunun. All the isolated lactic acid bacteria were non-motile, rod shaped gram positive organisms but catalase negative. They were Oxidase negative and did not hydrolyze Arginine (except for *L. fermentum*). Only one the organism showed delayed growth at 37°C (*L. sakei*).

Details of the results of sugar fermentation tests by isolated microorganisms are shown in Table 2. *L. acidophilus* produced acid/gas with glucose. It produced acids only with maltose, Galactose and lactose but it did not ferment mannitol, sucrose and Arabinose. *L. fermentum* followed the same pattern except that it also fermented sucrose with the production of only acid and showed delayed fermentation with Arabinose. *L. fermentum* produced acid/gas with maltose, glucose and lactose. It produced only acids with Galactose and Arabinose but did not ferment mannitol and sucrose. *L. sakei* produced acids with maltose, Galactose and sucrose; did not ferment Arabinose, mannitol and glucose but showed delayed fermentation with lactose. These characteristics were used to identify probable organisms since the genetic characteristics could not be determined to confirm their identity.

Inhibition of indicator organisms by Lactic acid bacteria:

Table 3 presents of inhibition of the pathogenic organisms *E. coli* and *S. aureus* by lactic acid bacteria used in the studies. The highest degree of inhibition for *E. coli* was exhibited by *L. fermentum* with an inhibition zone of (38mm) while the lowest degree of inhibition for this organism was exhibited by *L. acidophilus*. The same pattern of inhibition was observed for *S. aureus* (*L. fermentum* showed the highest inhibition level while *L. sakei* showed the lowest inhibition level). Inhibitions by the cell free supernatant of the overnight broth of the test organism (control) were similar but slightly lower in each case.

After treatment with proteinase K, inhibition was monitored again and the results are shown in Table 4.

While the level of inhibition originally exhibited by *L. sakei* and *L. acidophilus* decreased after treatment with proteinase K, inhibition by *L. planetarium* and *L. fermentum* was completely abolished. This clearly indicates that the metabolite(s) responsible for inhibition by *L. fermentum* and *L. plantarum* had a proteinaceous nature and would most probably be bacterocin while other metabolites was the major contributors contributed to the inhibitory activities of *L. sakei* and *L. acidophilus*. Bacterocin which are largely responsible for the inhibitory activity of *L. fermentum* and *L. sakei* are known probiotics which have been associated with health benefits, in addition to their preservative properties (Miles, 2007).

Table 1: Morphological characteristics of lactic acid bacteria isolated form Ogi and Kunun

Parameters	Isolates			
	I	II	III	IV
Morphology	Rod shaped			
Gram stain reaction	+ ve	+ ve	+ ve	+ ve
Motility	Non-motile	Non-motile	Non-motile	Non-motile
Catalasa test	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Oxidase test	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Arginine test	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Nitrate reduction test	-ve	-ve	-ve	-ve
Growth at 37°C	+ ve	+ ve	+ ve	Delayed growth
Probable organism	<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>	<i>Lactobacillus plantarium</i>	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	<i>Lactobacillus sakei</i>

Table 2: Sugar fermentation by lactic acid bacteria

Sugar	Organism			
	I	II	III	IV
Maltose	Acid	Acid	Acid/Gas	Acid
Glucose	Acid/Gas	Acid/Gas	Acid/Gas	-
Galactose	Acid	Acid	Acid	Acid
Mannitol	-	-	-	-
Lactose	Acid	Acid	Acid/Gas	Delayed growth
Sucrose	-	Acid	-	Acid
Arabinose	-	Delayed growth	Acid	-

Table 3: Inhibition of pathogenic organisms by lactic acid Bacteria before treatment with Proteinase K.

Lactobacillus bacteria Isolates	Inhibition zones for pathogenic bacteria (mm)			
	<i>E. coli</i>	Control	<i>S. aureus</i>	Control
<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	28	25	25	20
<i>Lactobacillus sakei</i>	30	28	25	23
<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i>	25	20	18	15
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	38	35	35	30

Control = Cell free supernatant of the over night broth of the test organism.

Table 4: Inhibition with Proteinase K. Enzyme.

Isolates	Pathogenic Organisms	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
Lactobacillus plantarium	No inhibition	No inhibition
Lactobacillus sakei	22mm	25mm
Lactobacillus acidophilus	20mm	23mm
Lactobacillus fermentum	No inhibition	No inhibition

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors acknowledge the financial support of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Senate research grant for this research work.

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Received for Publication: 24/01/2011

Accepted for Publication: 10/03/2011

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